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**Reimagining English Language Learning through AI-Assisted
Language Learning: A Study of Speaking Proficiency among ESL
Learners in Public Sector Colleges of District Rajanpur**

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Abstract

This research deals with the effect of AI-assisted language learning on the speaking proficiency of the ESL Learners. In addition to altering people's lifestyles, technology seems to have also altered how we communicate, work, and learn. Innovations of various kinds are always in transitions to make our activities more useful and efficient. A more recent technological development is the emergence of term "Artificial Intelligence" which is currently working as a tool. This tool was created in the form of programs and robots to enhance the speaking proficiency of the ESL learners. English Language is getting more and more importance in the recent era as it has occupied the status of instructions, social media and business communication almost all over the world. So, every ESL learner wants to speak in English. But, it has been observed that majority of ESL learners seem to struggle in their speaking proficiency in the underdeveloped District Rajanpur. Saraiki (L1) is used as a mode of communication in most public sector colleges of District Rajanpur. Learners are not facilitated with expert English language teachers and can't get good books on English language learning due to financial problem. It was observed that teachers and students do not give proper attention to communication skills. Keeping in view the significance of speaking proficiency, the artificial intelligence assisted language learning was introduced to fulfill this need. This study was experimental in nature and two variables i.e. Variable 1 and variable 2 were used to carry out this study. One was experimental group and other was traditional instruction group, each group carried 30 participants, hence the sample of this study was 60 in total. A pre – test and post – test was conducted to compare the data statistically. Artificial intelligence assisted language learning provided many contents based recorded videos to enhance the speaking proficiency of the ESL learners. This research tested the effectiveness of AI language learning aids in the enhancement of speaking ability among ESL students using virtual tutor system and speech recognition. The experimental group participants performed 11.7% better on their post-test with a mean number of 27.5 as compared with the control group which was 23.93, indicating that the use of AI enhanced the abilities of the participants.

Keywords: *Artificial intelligence language learning (AIALL), English as a second language learner (ESL)*

Introduction

Pakistan is a country in which many languages are spoken (Ahmad et al., 2022). The educated Pakistanis acquire some degree of proficiency in the elite class school system. This gives the Pakistani elite some degree of proficiency in L2 (Amjad et al., 2021). It is an investigation of the effect of artificial material on the speaking proficiency of the ESL learners in public sector colleges of District Rajanpur. Communication skills have always been a point of debate for the linguists (Chen & Ramzan, 2024; Li & Akram, 2023, 2024). First a learner and later a scholar of English language and the researchers have experienced that speaking skills have always been ignored in ESL classrooms (Ramzan et al., 2020, 2023, 2025). This study is an exploration to find out the effect of Artificial Intelligence on the speaking proficiency of the ESL learners in the public sector colleges of district Rajanpur.

Artificial intelligence

It is the ability of a machine or computer to conduct operations like learning, problem-solving, and language comprehension that normally call for human intelligence (Maa et al., 2024). The main goal of AI is to build machines that are capable of thinking and learning.

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Examples of AI include

Smart Assistants: AI is used by Siri and Alexa and other devices to comprehend and react to spoken requests.

Self-driving cars: AI is used by self-driving cars to traverse highways, make decisions, and avoid risks.

Machine learning: Machine learning: Algorithms, such as spam filters or recommender systems, learn from data to make decisions or predictions without specific programming.

Natural language processing: Chatbots and translation software are examples of how artificial intelligence (AI) allows robots to comprehend, interpret, and produce human language.

Image recognition: Systems used in facial recognition and security systems are able to recognize faces, objects, and other visual components in pictures and videos.

Fraud detection: Artificial intelligence (AI) is able to examine data and identify patterns that indicate fraudulent financial activities.

Robotics: Intelligent tasks like factory assembly and surgery can be carried out by robots.

Artificial intelligence assisted language learning.

AI is changing language learning by providing efficient, interactive, and customized resources. AI systems adjust to each learner, offering customized instruction, feedback, and conversation practice (Abdelrady et al., 2025, 2026). AI-powered applications frequently duplicate in-person interactions, provide immediate feedback, and even transcribe movies and podcasts (Akram & Abdelrady, 2023, 2025).

How AI helps with language learning:

Personalized learning: AI can assess a learner's strengths and shortcomings to generate learning paths that are specifically designed for them (Abdelrady & Akram, 2022).

Conversational practices: Real-time practice and feedback are made possible by AI chatbots and conversational interfaces.

Voice recognition: A lot of apps evaluate pronunciation and offer feedback by using voice recognition system.

Interactive lessons: AI is capable of producing interesting and dynamic lessons with questions and games.

Adaptive learning: AI is able to modify the level of difficulty of lessons according to the development of the student.

Examples of AI language learning app and tools:

- **Duolingo:** A gamified application that emphasizes fundamental abilities.
- **Speakpal:** It provides interactive conversations with an AI instructor.

Babbel: It places a strong emphasis on conversation practice and vocabulary.

- **Language:** It offers immediate feedback and emphasizes conversational practice.
- **Hello Talk:** It allows users to practice conversations with native speakers.
- **Hallo:** It provides language tests powered by AI.
- **Berlitz:** This AI program is used for language learning and evaluation.

Research Questions

What is the effect of artificial intelligence assisted language learning on the speaking proficiency of ESL learners in the public sector colleges of district Rajanpur?

Significance of the study

It is a point to ponder that our students have studied English as a compulsory subject till intermediate, but they are unable to speak in English language. They face this problem not only during their presentations in the classes but in their professional life as well. They are on the horns of dilemma when they are asked to speak in English language, they become hesitant. The increased importance of English has demanded the students to be more fluent in English and to be a fine speaker of English language. They should be comprehensible in conveying and communicating their tasks. Pakistani students also want to attain proficiency in English language. This study is incredibly useful for the teachers of English language at BS-level and for the ESL learners in the public sector colleges of district Rajanpur.

Literature Review

Artificial Intelligence Assisted Language Learning (AIALL) has emerged as a promising tool in language learning (Javaid & Ramzan, 2026), offering adaptive learning experiences to students (Akram et al., 2021, 2022). This literature review explores the role of AIALL in enhancing the speaking proficiency of English as Second Language (ESL) learners, particularly focusing on a study conducted in the public sector colleges of

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District Rajanpur.

Zhai and Wibowo (2023) have reviewed studies on using AI dialogue systems in classrooms to help improve interactional skills of ESL university students, and revealed the six factors with 25 sub-factors impacting dialogue systems. The review was based on the studies done before 2021, before generative AI systems. The survey found that dialogue systems can be practiced interactional skills but the absence of elements of argumentative skills and problem solving skills in dialogue systems. Most recent review is by Kundu and Bej (2025) who explored the studies of AI use in ESL classroom by reviewing the empirical studies to deliver an overview and impact of using AI in the classrooms for school? They have reviewed the studies conducted from 2020-2024 which have impact on primary-secondary education.

AIALL systems employ various technologies such as Natural Language Processing (NLP), Machine Learning (ML), and speech recognition to provide interactive and tailored language learning experiences. These systems offer opportunities for learners to engage in authentic communication, receive immediate feedback, and access customized learning materials, thereby enhancing their language skills. Eliza was to show the awkwardness of pattern matching (chat) man-machine communication Kuipers, McCarthy and Weizenbaum (1976). We need research the importance of meaning focused dialogue, share ability of language skills and university problem and discussion skills. AI dialogue systems is a computer program that mimics human dialogue interaction (text or voice). This can either be through natural language processing (NLP), machine learning or deep learning. The past ten years we have witnessed the rise of AI dialogue systems as research indicates that this kind of dialogue system is easily used, non-judgmental and, as a result, provides a positive-boosting environment AlTwijri and Alghizzi (2024). A couple of years ago we used AI dialogue systems primarily for health, marketing, business, e-commerce, entertainment and even learning a language.

Numerous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of AIALL in improving ESL learners' proficiency, especially in speaking skills. Asratie, Wale, and Aylet (2023). For instance, a study found that ESL students exposed that AIALL showed significant improvement in speaking fluency, accuracy, and confidence compared to those in traditional classrooms.

AIALL platforms can analyze learner's performance data to provide personalized learning paths and adaptive feedback. This individualized approach caters to the diverse needs and learning styles of ESL learners, fostering greater engagement and motivation Alyousef, H. S. (2006).

Despite its potential benefits, the integration of AIALL in ESL learning faces certain challenges. Technical limitations, access to resources, and concerns regarding the authenticity of communication are some of the primary obstacles Wehbe and Burns, M. (2013). Moreover, the role of teachers in facilitating meaningful interactions and scaffolding learning remains crucial in AIALL environments Kim, J., Lee, H., & Cho, Y. H. (2022). The effectiveness of AIALL in ESL learning can be influenced by various contextual factors, including learners' proficiency level, cultural backgrounds, and educational settings. Previous experiments have been using AI to help language learning strategies with English as second language (ESL) and English as foreign language (ESL) either in writing Fitria, T. N. (2023, March). This literature review synthesizes previous research on the role of AIALL in developing the speaking proficiency of ESL learners at the BS level. It underscores the potential of AIALL to enhance language learning outcomes through personalized instruction, adaptive feedback, and pedagogical sound design. By addressing contextual factors and challenges, future research can contribute to a deeper understanding of how AIALL can effectively support ESL learners in achieving the English-speaking language proficiency. Oliver, R., Vanderford, S., & Grote, E. (2012)

Research Methodology

Research methodology is regarded as the basis of each research work; without it, there could be no research. In every kind of study, a researcher starts with a problem and tries to find out the solutions.

Research methodology is a way to identify a particular challenge. Once a research problem has been detected, the different methods are used to solve it are commonly referred as research methodology. According to the Industrial Research Institute (2010), "methodology" refers to the process of looking for or resolving the research challenge. The current research project is experimental in nature.

According to Goddard, W., & Melville, S. (2004). research is defined as a process of enquiry and investigation; it is systematic, methodical and ethical; research can help to solve practical problems and increase knowledge. Howard and Sharp defined it in this way: a methodical process of getting insights and discovering vital facts by adding our own knowledge and of others as well. Research patterns are particularly important in every research.

The research methodology is considered a backbone in research work if there is no method then there is no research, in every type of research a researcher takes an issue. Research methodology is a mode to catch distinctive difficulty when a research problem is noticed then how it is solved or attained that process is called the research methodology. If we think about the word “Methodology” it is the way of searching or solving the research problem (Industrial research institute 2010). Research methodology can be defined as an intellectual human activity which is used in the exploration of matter and nature specifically the way in which data is collected, organized, explained and analyzed. Goddard and Melville (2004) argue, “In a research methodology, researcher always tries to investigate and interpret the question systematically and to find out the answer of the problem until conclusion. If the researcher does not find the answer to the problem or question, there will be less possibility to reaching the conclusion. A researcher can face problems in finding answer to the questions; but this problem can be sorted out by using correct research methodology (Industrial research institute, 201)

As the main objective of this study was to explore the effect of Artificial intelligence assisted language learning tools on the speaking proficiency of the ESL learners at public sector colleges of District Rajanpur, pre-test and post-test research tools of the experimental research design were mainly used. It was compulsory for researchers to define and explain explicitly, the sample and population of the study. In this research, there were no hard and fast rules, and the researcher has to rely on his own judgment and reasoning. The population of the study was defined according to the aims and objectives of the study. The situation and demand of the study decided the choice of the target population. The features of the selected population were represented by the sample of the research study. The subjects of the study were 60 ESL learners in the public sector colleges of district Rajanpur, as both classes of 30 students (in each group) were selected from BS English classes. This research aims to explore how Artificial intelligence assisted language learning tools can be used in ESL classes for acquiring better speaking proficiency in the public sector colleges of District Rajanpur to provide the learners a productive environment for learning. Further, the various data collection tools were used for this study. The research was based on experimental design. Two groups of participants experimentally and controlled were randomly selected from public sector colleges of District Rajanpur. There were 30 students in each group. Pre-test and Post-test were conducted for both of these two groups. Before, applying any general method, a pre-test was conducted for both groups and after the treatment the Post-test is conducted to find out the results. The earlier condition of the groups from their present condition and the difference showed the effectiveness of the treatment. Experimental research is significant to society as it helps us to improve our everyday life. The experimental method is a systematic and scientific approach to research for the researcher’s variables and controls any change in other variable i.e. before and after the treatment, the ESL learner’s speaking proficiency was improved by experimental research. Researchers arranged one or more variable to find out change in variable in experimental method which remained systematic and scientific approach. Pre-test results were gathered for both student groups. After the pre-test, three months of treatment was planned, during which time different methods and approaches were employed to enhance the speaking proficiency of ESL-learners. A post-test with material similar to the pre-test was applied and the data was gathered in the form of scores. The information was recorded, evaluated and interpreted as per group. The statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) was used to evaluate the data, and the appropriate one sample Paired T-test was also used.

Group Statistics

Groups		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mea
Post Test	Traditional Group	30	23.9333	2.27328	.41504
	Experimental Group	30	27.5000	1.13715	.20761

For both the standard and experimental groups, two samples of thirty students each were collected. Prior to administering treatment, each group underwent homogeneity testing, as described below. Table 5 shows that the average scores for the experimental group were 27.5, whereas the average scores for the traditional group were 23.93. For the traditional group, the standard difference and standard error are 2.27328 and 1.917, while for the experimental group, they are 1.13715 and 0.20761.

Discussion of the Results

It's quite clear from the results of this study that learner's English language speaking proficiency has improved rapidly by using AI assisted language learning tools and applications for enhancing speaking proficiency of the ESL learners in the public sector colleges of district Rajanpur. Moreover, larger proportion of the ESL learners is reaching a proficient level on standardized tests which shows progress on educational development as well.

The researchers have concluded that the students enjoyed this program in learning the English-speaking proficiency by using different AI application; they have viewed that this project has assisted them in a great deal in learning the speaking skills and it has also enhanced their academic growth. When we check all these aspects, it defines that learners are getting the benefits from this project.

The data collected from the study showed that the ESL learners' response was well after the treatment of AI assisted language learning tools for learning of English-speaking skills. All the students responded well and enjoyed themselves while interacting with the AIALL program. Finally, the researcher concluded that the ESL learner's growth in learning the speaking skill is faster than the learners who do not use this program.

The findings of the investigation showed that there was a significant statistical difference between the post-test results of experimental group and the post-test results of control group. This research work showed that the experimental group benefited largely by using AIALL program in learning English speaking skills. This defined that AIALL program for learning the language was a helpful tool for the rapid learning of English-speaking skills.

The results of present investigation showed that AIALL material of learning the English-speaking skill has a significant effect on learners' speaking proficiency.

By using AIALL tools or applications English language learners have become able to compare their performance, and they can learn the language in a better way. The program which has been used in learning the English-speaking skills permits the ESL learners to use the program themselves in or out of their classrooms whenever they desire. This project has allowed them to process the information about learning in a straightforward way.

The AIALL tools used in the current investigation enabled the ESL learners of the experimental group to practice different sub-skills of speaking which they consider particularly useful for them. Learners of the experimental group showed great progress in correcting out their speaking skills as compared to the control group. They were able to check their grammatical mistakes while speaking English by the use of AIALL applications on speaking proficiency again and again.

ESL learners of the experimental group performed better in correcting out their pronunciation mistakes while speaking English language. The learners who were taught by the use of AIALL tools performed better than the learners who were treated with traditional methods.

Thus, the results of the present study demonstrate that AIALL tools are useful for learning important sub-skills of language particularly English speaking skill. It is a notable phenomenon that learners' linguistic development covers all linguistic features which the program has presented, i.e., grammar, pronunciation, spelling and style. The population of the experimental group, who had the access to the learning facilities like AIALL applications for learning of speaking skills and they have performed much better; as they had the facilities available inside and outside the classroom whenever they wanted for the learning of English-speaking

skills.

Conclusion

This research tested the effectiveness of AI language learning aids in the enhancement of speaking ability among ESL students using virtual tutor system and speech recognition. The experimental group participants performed 11.7% better on their post-test with a mean number of 27.5 as compared to the control group which was 23.9333, indicating that learning of speaking comprehension by the use of AI enhanced the abilities of the participants. The pre-test and post-test mean scores for the Traditional and Experimental groups are displayed in a clustered bar chart. It is evident that both groups' mean scores increased from the pre-test to the post-test, suggesting a general improvement in performance as time goes by. At both stages, the Experimental group's mean scores are higher than those of the Traditional group, indicating comparatively greater performance.

The activities based on combination of AI tools and live feedback with interactive approaches lead to better oral language processing and pattern recognition capabilities and accent comprehension among learners. The research demonstrated that educational programs should strike a balance between AI technology and conventional teaching practices to achieve the best student outcomes. Learners who used AIALL tools for the learning of English-speaking skills achieved higher mean scores in their post-test after the treatment than their scores in their pre-test before the conduction of experiment. Learners who used AIALL tools to enhance their speaking ability obtained considerably better proficiency than learners of the conventional classroom who were given instruction by the traditional method, verifying that AI is an effective tool for learning better speaking proficiency, pronunciation and style. This application of the AIALL program supported learner-centered approach, autonomy skills and problem-solving strategies. The learners used most of the linguistic features accessible in the AIALL programs for their individual needs. This AI-based program allows ESL learners to obtain a kind of response which he or she needs.

Implications of the Study

The main purpose of current study was to present an effective method of teaching English-speaking skills to the ESL learners. The findings of current investigation or study suggested the following key points; Learners can get benefits from the learning of English-speaking skills with the useful application of AIALL tools on speaking proficiency. Learners can become more self-directed and interested in the use of AIALL applications for improving their English-speaking proficiency. The use of AIALL tools at home by the ESL learners increased their English-speaking proficiency, for example, it is an expansion in the time and place of the learning of speaking tasks. The Use of AI program for the learning of the speaking skills or any other error checking program for speaking proficiency enables the ESL learners to have an approach to the update valuable linguistic features for checking, correcting and evaluating errors in their speaking proficiency. Such kinds of programs are particularly useful in providing response on error type, examples and linguistic rules.

Recommendations

There is a set of recommendations proposed for both teachers and policymakers, as well as for researchers.

1. The teachers should combine AI-assisted techniques with traditional educational methods to improve student's growth.
2. Real-time speech recognition systems equipped with feedback tools should be implemented to enable students in improving their pronunciation, their stress and intonation skills.
3. Learners should use AI virtual tutors and chatbots for their exposure to natural language inputs that enhance their understanding as speaking is part of their learning process.
4. Students should be involved in training to master AI-based tools properly, so they learn independent speaking methods beyond AI feedback dependence.
5. Educational institutions should create curriculum equipped with AI-supported learning systems for ESL students during speaking activities.
6. AI-learning tools should be made accessible to every the ESL learners, especially for those who are in underdeveloped areas.
7. There should be a trend of creation of artificial intelligence models in all the English classrooms of all the institutions of Pakistan so that the learners may improve their English-speaking skill.
8. The AIALL programs may be used more in Pakistan, especially in the underdeveloped areas like Rajanpur so that learners speaking proficiency may be increased.

9. Educational management of Pakistan is advised to include AIALL facilities in their educational programs for learners and teachers for getting better learning outcomes.

10. The Government of Pakistan should provide AIALL training to the English language teachers for improving their English-speaking skills, which will be further delivered by trained teachers to the ESL learners.

11. As the use of AI- technology in Pakistan is increasing day by day so it is recommended for the government to develop AI-equipped multimedia labs and promote AI programs in ESL classes.

12. The ESL learners should be advised to use artificial intelligence for improving their education as it is a normal part of their education system and it is not something out of their routine.

13. The suitable AI-based drill practices should be connected with English subject in educational institutions for imparting instructions to the ESL learners. AI can serve as a tutor who makes available the skills for practice and language learning drills.

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